

KNOWLEDGE AND AWARENESS OF HEALTH PROVIDERS AND THE GENERAL POPULATION TOWARDS PHOSPHO- DI-ESTERASE-INHIBITORS (PDE5I) DRUGS

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Article Received: April 2020

Accepted: May 2020

Published: June 2020

Abstract:

Background: Phosphodiesterase-5 inhibitors (PDE5I) are common worldwide first-line medical therapy for erectile dysfunction. Many studies have reported the recreational use of PDE5I by healthy males who lack the knowledge of the risks of this use. This study aims to assess the knowledge, awareness, and practice of medical professionals, as well as the general population towards the use of PDE5I.

Methods: This is a cross-sectional survey-based study divided into two questionnaires, which were carried from October 2019 to January 2020. The surveys were applied to healthcare providers (pharmacists and physicians) as well as the general population. All data were collected first into Microsoft Excel sheet version 2016 then transferred to SPSS version 25.0 to be analyzed.

Results: A total of 486 participants were involved in this research. Among them, 346 were a general population and 140 healthcare providers. Three-fourths (77.1%) of healthcare providers perform routine medical interviews including taking medical history before prescribing or selling PDE5I and the two third of them (62.2%) referred patients to specialized physician. Only 31.5% of the general population use PDE5I. Two-thirds (61.9%) use it out of curiosity and 78.2% who received the drug from the pharmacy reported that pharmacists do not ask for a prescription before selling the drug. Low levels of awareness have been found among the general population including awareness of side effects and contraindications of PDE5I.

Conclusion: PDE5I are commonly prescribed and used in Eastern Province, Saudi Arabia for recreational purposes. Healthcare providers not have enough knowledge of PDE5I drugs while the majority of the general population is unaware of adverse effects, seriousness or contraindications of PDE5I use for ED. Urgent need for strict low and regulations to restrict the access of PDE5I drugs may be indicated.

Keywords: PDE5I; erectile dysfunction (ED); recreational.

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Please cite this article in press Hamed Mohammed Eldarawany et al., **Knowledge And Awareness Of Health Providers And The General Population Towards Phospho-Di-Esterase-Inhibitors (PDE5I) Drugs.**, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2020; 07(06).

INTRODUCTION:

Erectile dysfunction (ED) is the failure to initiate or sustain an erection that last enough for a sexual activity¹ Erectile dysfunction (ED) is a multi-dimensional disorder which has an estimated prevalence ranging from 1% - 10% in males younger than 40 years and all the way to 100% in males in their 70's and 80's, rates are higher in the United States and Southeast Asia than in Europe.² It is estimated to affect 322 million people worldwide³ Although ED is not a life-threatening disorder, its effect on the quality-of-life is quite considerable.¹

There are multiple management choices for ED. One of which is phosphodiesterase type 5 inhibitor (PDE5I) oral therapy⁴, ever since sildenafil was first approved back in 1998 by the European Medicine Agency (EMA), PDE5I have revolutionized the evaluation and management of ED.^{5,6}

These drugs have a similar mechanism of action, where the production of cGMP triggers the relaxing of the arterial and the trabecular smooth muscle, which would cause the arteries to dilate and the veins to constrict, resulting in an erection.⁷

Currently, PDE5I is the most effective and well-tolerated type of medication for management of ED. However, their misuse by men without ED is seen as a serious health issue. PDE5I without a doubt are among the most misused medications, and their recreational use has vastly outstripped their therapeutic use.^{8,9}

such practice would, without a doubt, cause serious and unanticipated negative effects, especially if PDE5Is were to be combined with the use of alcohols, illicit drugs, and psychotropic medication or in the presence of concomitant medical conditions.¹⁰ PDE5I considered as contradiction in unstable angina, recent diagnosis with myocardial infarction, arrhythmias and uncontrolled hypertension as well as guanilate cyclase stimulators and nitrates.¹¹

The recreational use of PDE5I may be due easy access and the lack of strict regulations that control handling of those type of medications. PDE5I can be easily and illegally purchased and acquired without prescriptions from pharmacies.¹²

The recreational use of PDE5I may be related to lack of knowledge in between general populations, non-specialized physician, and/or the pharmacists about the medications, its indications and contraindications.

In this study, we investigated the knowledge, attitude of PDE5I users among Saudi men in

eastern province, as well as the knowledge, attitude of PDE5I providers (pharmacists, and non-specialized physician) in eastern province, Saudi Arabia.

Aim of the study:

To measure the awareness and knowledge about phospho-di-esterase-inhibitors (PDE5I) drugs, indications, duration, dosage, drug interaction, contraindication and side effect among the PDE5I drug users as well as the non-specialized PDE5I drug health providers (Primary health care physicians, pharmacists) in the east province of Saudi Arabia.

METHODS & PARTICIPANTS:**Study Design and Setting:**

This is a cross-sectional survey-based study done in Saudi Arabian population.

Sampling and Data Collection:

The targeted population were healthcare providers as well as a sample of the general population. All whom agreed to take part were included. The total sample consisted of 486 participants. All of which were literate Saudi males whom were able to understand the questionnaire.

A pre-designed disseminated questionnaire was distributed for data collection during the period (October 2019 to January 2020). Inclusion criteria: participants enrolled in this study were male, adults, Saudi, who completed and filled the form correctly.

Exclusion criteria: those unwilling to participate, and those whom did not understand the questions properly and/or have answered the form incorrectly.

Data Collection Tools:

We designed two questionnaires, one designed for healthcare providers in English language and the other for the participants of general male population in Arabic language. Participants were approached with a self-administered questionnaire to be filled by them with the guidance of the data collectors, as well we used test-retest method for both questionnaires. A letter that explains the objectives of the study and asks for participants consent was attached to the questionnaire. The surveys intended to evaluate the demographic distribution of family physicians, pharmacists and other non-specialized doctors who prescribe PDE5I. First questionnaire (questionnaire 1) for healthcare providers was designed to assess the awareness and knowledge of indications, duration, dosage, drug interaction, contraindication and side effects. Second questionnaire (questionnaire 2) for the general population to assess who used PDE5I,

causes of usage, level of education, duration, dosage, side effects, awareness and knowledge.

Sample Size:

We anticipated a high response rate; however, we eliminated all invalid, incomplete responses and any responses that did not line with the inclusion criteria with a total of 486 respondents.

Data Management and Statistical Analysis:

The collected data was entered and analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS Inc. Chicago, IL, USA) version 23. Descriptive statistics were performed. Percentages were given for qualitative variables.

Ethical Considerations:

The participants were informed that participating is completely voluntary. All the participants were aware that their data would be handled confidentially. No names were written in the forms and the data was kept safely.

RESULTS:

In this study, a total of 486 participant were involved, divided into 2 groups. The first group involved 140 male health service responders (nonspecialized general practitioners, family medicine physician, pharmacists and other doctors) while the second group involved 346 male participants from the general population. In the first group, general practitioners (GPs) represent 53/140 (37.9%) of the participants, while pharmacists represent 33/140 (23.6%), family physicians represent 30/140 (21.4%), and other non-specialized specialties represent 24/140 (17.1%) (Table 1).

On the second group, the representations of general population responders were, college students 90/346 (26.3%), medical students 81/346 (23.4%), health employee 48/346 (13.9%), and retired individuals 36/346 (10.4%) while employees of different sectors represent 90/346 (26%) of responders (Table 1). 156/346 (45.1%) of general population responders were married and 190/346 (54.9%) were single individuals (Table 1).

In the first group, about 11/33 (34.0%) of the pharmacist were used to prescribe PDE5I while 16/53 (29.8%) of general practitioners (GPs) and 6/30 (21.3%) family medicine physician were found to prescribe this type of medications. The majority of family medicine physician and general practitioners 98/140 (70%) were found to know the proper time for taking PDE5I medications, they stated that, PDE5I drugs should be taken 2- 4 hours prior to intercourse, while 42/140 (30%) of first group responders did not know the proper time of taking PDE5I drugs.

When assessing if the first group responders perform routine medical interview with the patients or not, 108/140 (77.1%) of first group were found to have a detailed medical history from the patient before prescribing or selling PDE5I, while 32/140 (22.9%) of them did not have any medical history from the patients (Table 2). About 87/140 (62.1%) of first group responders had referred patients to specialized physician while 53/140 (37.9%) had not (Table 2).

When assessing the knowledge of the first group responders about side effects of the PDE5I drugs, about (16.0%), (12.5%), (11.4%) and (6.3%) of the first group agreed that the drug has the following side effects, headache and flushing, dyspepsia, nasal congestion and painful erection for more than 6 hours respectively (Table 2). On the other hand only (38.6%) of the first group always explain the side effect to the patients, while (25.7%) usually did, (11.4%) not often explain the side effect to the patients and (24.3%) never inform the patients about the possible side effect of PDE5I drugs (Table2).

Regarding the knowledge of the first group about the contraindications of the PDE5I drugs, it was found that, 116/140 (82.9%) of the first group claimed that they know the contraindications of PDE5I while 24/140 (17.1%) stated that they do not know (Table 2). On the other, hand (35.0%) of the first group stated that the PDE5I drugs are contraindicated in patient receiving nitrite drugs, (31.2%) of them agreed that the PDE5I drugs are contraindicated in cardiac patients while 33.8% of the first group did not know the contraindications of the PDE5I drugs (Table 2).

In the second group, 237 male (68.5%) denied using PDE5I at all, 76 male (22%) used it on several occasions and 33 male (9.5%) have used it once. Of the 109 people who have used PDE5I drugs, 42/109 (38.1%) reported that they used PDE5I as a treatment while 67/109 (61.9%) were used it for recreational purposes. About 211/346 (61.1%) of the second group responders knows about PDE5I medications from their friends, while 77/346 (22.2%) got their information from the media and advertisements and 58/346 (16.8%) got the PDE5I information from their doctors (Table 3).

In the second group, 77/109 (70.4%) received the drug from the pharmacy, 21/109 (19.4%) received the drug from their friend and only 11/109 (10.2%) from hospital (Table3). Those who received the drug from the pharmacy, 60/77 (78.2%) mentioned that they got PDE5I from the pharmacy without prescription while 17/77 (21.8%) received the PDE5I with prescription (Table 3). Those who received the drugs from the pharmacist without

prescriptions, 29.9% were asked from the pharmacist about reason of taking this type of medications while 70.1% were not asked. Also, 58.5% participants were not asked if they have hypertension or not while 42.5% were asked. About 57.5% were not asked if they are taking nitrites or not while 42.5% were asked.

aware of the side effects of the PDE5I while 54/109 (49.4%) were not aware (Table 3). 78/109 (71.6%) of participants were not aware about the contraindications of PDE5I drugs while 31/109 (28.4%) were aware about the contraindications of PDE5I drugs (table 3).

Regarding to knowledge and awareness of the PDE5I users, 55/109 (50.6%) of participants were

Table 1: Demographic distributions of first and second groups.

Total 486	First group (providers of PDE5I) 140/486	Second group (General male responders) 346/486
	GPs 53/140 (37.9%) Pharmacists 33/140 (23.6%) Family medicine 30/140 (21.4%) Other doctors 24/140 (17.1%)	College students 91/346 (26.3%) Employees of different sectors 90/346 (26.0%) Medical students 81/346 (23.4%) Health employee 48/346 (13.9%) Retired individuals 36/346 (10.4%)
		Marital status
		Married 156/346 (45.1%) Single 190/346 (54.9%)

GPs=General practitioners

Table 2: Knowledge and awareness of the first group responders.

<i>First group</i>	Total 140
<i>Drug prescription</i>	
Total	36/140(26%)
Pharmacist	11/33 (34.0%)
GPs	16/53 (29.8%)
Family medicine	6/30 (21.3%)
Others	7/24 (12.5%)
<i>Knowledge about the proper time of taking medications</i>	
Total	140
Knows	98/140 (70%)
Do not knows	42/140 (30%)
<i>Knowledge about PDE5I contraindications</i>	
Total	140
Knows the contraindications	116/140 (82.9%)
Contraindications with nitrites	49/116 (42.2%)
Contraindications with cardiac patient	44/116 (37.9%)
Contraindications with nitrites and cardiac	23/116 (19.8%)
Do not knows the contraindications	24/140 (17.1%)
<i>Knowledge about PDE5I side effects</i>	
<i>total</i>	140
Knows	65/140 (46.4%)
Do not knows	75/140 (53.6%)
<i>Did they inform PDE5I users of the side effects</i>	
<i>total</i>	75
user was always informed about side effects of the PDE5I	30/75 (38.6%)
user was usually informed about side effects of the PDE5I	19/75 (25.7%)

user was not often informed about side effects of the PDE5I	8/75 (11.4%)
user was never informed about side effects of the PDE5I	18/75 (24.3%)
History taking	
Total	140
Received detailed history from the PDE5I users	108/140 (77.1%)
Did not receive any history from the PDE5I users	32/140 (22.9%)
Referral to specialised service	
Total	140
Referred the PDE5I users from specialised service	87/140 (62.1%)
Did not refer the PDE5I user to specialised service	53/140 (37.9%)

GPs=General practitioners

Table 3: Knowledge and awareness of the second group responders.

Second group	Total 346
PDE5I users	109/346 (31.5%)
As treatment	42/109 (38.1%)
recreational	67/109 (61.9%)
PDE5I nonusers	237/346 (68.5%)
Source of PDE5I drugs for the users	
Total	109
Pharmacy	77/109 (70.4%)
Without prescription	60/77 (78.2%)
With prescription	17/77 (21.8%)
Friends	21/109 (19.4%)
hospital	11/109 (10.2%)
Source of PDE5I drugs knowledge	
Total	346
From friends	211/346 (61.1%)
From media	77/346 (22.2%)
From doctors	58/346 (16.8%)
PDE5I users awareness of drugs side effect	
total	109
Aware	55/109 (50.6%)
Not aware	54/109 (49.9%)
PDE5I users awareness of the drugs contraindications	
total	109
Aware	31/109 (28.4%)
Not aware	78/109 (71.6%)

PDE5I=phosphodiesterase 5 inhibitor

DISCUSSION:

In this directly and internet distributed based questionnaire study, we distinguished 2 subgroups, first group includes non-specialized health service providers who have the facilities to prescribe or to provide of PDE5I drugs, while the other group

includes males of general populations above the age of 18 years who may use the PDE5I drugs. The questionnaire that distributed for the first group (questionnaire 1) is different from the one distributed for the second group (questionnaire 2).

The first group included 140 responders while the second group included 346 responders.

The main indication for PDE5I medications is treatment of erectile dysfunctions (ED), but unfortunately, the PDE5I drug users tried PDE5I either for treatment or for recreational purposes. It was found that, shortly after sildenafil was launched in 1998, in spite of these drugs being approved for treating ED patients, authors have reported its recreational use¹¹

It was proven that, for the past decade, there was an increasing amount of young males, with no confirmed diagnosis of ED using PDE5I drug, in hope of improving their sexual performance¹³ In our study it was found that, 67/109 (61.9%) are using the PDE5I for recreational purposes to increase their sexual performances and 21/109 (19.4%) of them got the drugs from friends while 60/109 (55%) purchases those drugs non-officially from the pharmacies.

Our results are nearly similar to the results of several studies^{9,10,14,15} which reported the use of the PDE5I by young healthy males (usually university students) for recreational purposes.

Another population-based study has reported that the recreational use of PDE5I mainly occurs among young males between 18 to 44 years of age, whom had no definite erectile dysfunction^{12,16,17}.

This wide spread of recreational use of PDE5I is also reported by another study performed in Saudi Arabia in which 61.9% of 370 PDE5I users received the drugs for recreational purposes.¹³

One main cause for recreational use of PDE5I medications is easy and illegal access of those drugs. Saad A and his colleagues reported in their study that, nearly two-thirds of PDE5I users stated that they could easily acquire the drug from an acquaintance, from pharmacies without a prescription, or from different channels.¹³

Even many of ED patients in some studies have gotten their ED medication from an illegal non-healthcare provider source^{18,19} as most of the patients with ED did not discuss the issue with a specialized physician due to mainly dissatisfaction at the relationship with physicians and their inability to handle sexual concerns. Of 5,184 European males who self-reported ED, more than 50% didn't consult a physician about their condition, regardless of age. Therefore, most of them access those drugs away from the health services²⁰

The main illegal source of PDE5I are friends, pharmacies, and online sources. European survey

estimated that in Europe, around 6 million males have bypassed the health-care system to acquire a PDE5I.²¹ Another study showed that more than half (56.5%) acquired PDE5I drugs through an acquaintance.¹³

In this study we found that many of non-specialized health care providers are prescribing PDE5I. About (34.0%) of the pharmacist were prescribing PDE5I while (29.8%) of general practitioners (GPs) and (21.3%) family medicine physician prescribed this type of medications. In our study, 70.4% received the drug from the pharmacy, 19.4% received the drug from their friend and only 10.2% from hospital. Those who received the drug from the pharmacy, 78.2% mentioned that they got PDE5I without prescription.

The illegal easy access of PDE5I addresses the immediate need to reinforce firm regulations and to maintain constant supervision of the pharmacies as well as more investigation are needed for better understanding how to deal with the ED disease.

Another reason that may lead to increase in the recreational use or illegal access of PDE5I drugs is lack of knowledge of both the PDE5I drug providers and users about the indications, contraindications and the side effects of PDE5I medications.

In this study, 66/77 (78.2%) of PDE5I users who got the drugs from pharmacy without prescription received the drug easily and they were not asked from the pharmacist about the reason of taking this type of medications. Also, 58.5% were not asked if they have hypertension or not and 57.5% were not asked if they are taking nitrates medications or not. This indicate that either careles behavior or lack of knowledge of the pharmacists.

When assessing the knowledge of the first group responders about side effects and the contraindications of the PDE5I, the results were found disappointing. Only about (16.0%), (12.5%), (11.4%) and (6.3%) of the first group agreed that the drug has the following side effects, headache and flushing, dyspepsia, nasal congestion and painful erection for more than 6 hours respectively and about (24.3%) of PDE5I providers never inform the patients about the possible side effect. Even with assessment of the knowledge of the first group about the contraindications of the PDE5I, about 33.8% of PDE5I providers did not know the contraindications of the PDE5I drugs.

The lack of knowledge is also expected among the PDE5I users. In this study, 49.4% of PDE5I users were unaware of the side effects of PDE5I drugs,

74.7% were not aware of how to use the PDE5I drugs, and 71.6 % were found to have no information about the contraindications of PDE5I drugs.

The lack of knowledge of both providers and PDE5I users will add more hazardous effect to both the patients and health service system. Accordingly, more effort is needed from the health system to improve the basic knowledge of the patients and health provider about the PDE5I drugs.

Limitations of the present study are: 1- Low number of both PDE5I drug users and providers. More numbers of participants are needed for better and accurate results. 2- It was challenging to ascertain that the questions were understood and interpreted in the same way by various respondents. 3- The data presented here is self-reported, some of the respondents may report radical feedbacks compared to others, according to their beliefs and motivations. These factors may have affected the validity of the data and the results of the study. Therefore, a further prospective study is necessary in order to prove such a relationship.

CONCLUSION:

There is an increasing number of recreational PDE5I drugs users among the general male populations in eastern province of Saudi Arabia. This observation was found to be related to the easy feasibility and uncontrolled access of those types of drugs as well as lack of knowledge about the PDE5I drugs among both PDE5I users and providers. This may raise the issue of urgent need for strict laws and regulations to restrict the access of PDE5I drugs that should be given to only patients who have prescriptions. more studies focusing on psychosocial determinants of ED and PDE5I use in the younger population are warranted.

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